

THE DRAWBACKS IN LEARNING LISTENING COMPREHENSION

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This article informs about commonly encountered troubles such as phonological unawareness, background information, word recognition and reduced forms in getting effective listening skill. And also it gives possible solutions to advance listening comprehension.

Аннотация

В этой статье рассказывается о часто встречающихся проблемах, таких как фонологическая неосведомленность, фоновая информация, распознавание слов и редуцированные формы при получении эффективного навыка аудирования. А также дает возможные решения для улучшения понимания на слух.

Key words: audio materials, tape script, meaning, new words.

Ключевые слова: аудиоматериалы, сценарий ленты, смысл, новые слова.

INTRODUCTION

It is important to maximize efficiency of listening skill for foreign language learners. According to some scholars, for second language/foreign language learners, listening is the skill that makes the heaviest processing demands because learners must store information in short term memory at the same time as they are working to understand the information. In addition to this, they face up to the following obstacles:

Background information. It is actual fact that materials for listening comprehension consist of a mixed variety of scientific and cultural information. In Ahkam Hasan Assaf's

point of view, if foreign language learners do not know about the different aspects of second language culture, they will come across issues in listening comprehension [1, p.20]. As a result, this brings about lack of absolutely complete comprehension. But by listening different audio materials related to any thing is the best solution to prevent possible troubles while testing listening. It can be significantly helpful for listening practice. It can increase background information significantly.

Phonological unawareness. Rost stated that effective speech recognition involved an automated knowledge of the phonotactic system of a language [4, p.54]. That's why some students who have lack of phonological knowledge have problems to comprehend proper phonemes during listening comprehension. For tackling this problem, students must gain phonological knowledge and listen tape script of words. Then revising by spelling phonemes is reliable practice to keep gained knowledge in mind.

Word recognition. Some of foreign learners tend to get stressed to learn new words. For this reason, they may have difficulties with dealing with new words during listening comprehension. According to the research of Andi Asmawati, 85 % of students stop listening and think about the meaning of the word while coming across an unknown word. Actually it doesn't matter importantly all the time in order to answer questions properly [2, p.213]. Andi Asmawati stated that because of this reason they miss vital data. In stead of paying particular attention to unknown words, they must try to comprehend general meaning of context. So ignorance of new word's interpretation in the listening tasks is the best way to keep in touch with speakers if that word doesn't have to be written in order to complete statements.

Reduced forms. Gary Buck considered that a test type is related to the redundancy tests in many ways [3, p.30]. Andi Asmawati found out that many students have a lot of misunderstanding with releasing the meaning of reduced forms [2, p.214]. It occurs owing to poor grammar knowledge. That's why, it is crucial to get enough knowledge on grammar connected with redundancy for foreign language learners.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, if language learners have eagerness to learn a foreign language they have to try to gain enough knowledge as well as regular practice. And also they should talk to native speakers by social networks. It would be natural and effective practice for them. Importantly, belief in their efforts is a key solution any problem.

References

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